

Forest Elephants Modulate their Behavior to Adapt to Sounds of Danger

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1 **Abstract**

2 The African forest elephant (*Loxodonta cyclotis*) plays a critical role in upholding the Congo
3 Basin's structure and function, a vital area that supports global carbon sequestration. However,
4 between 1990-2021, the species' numbers declined by 86%, mainly due to ivory hunting. Due to
5 their elusive nature in the region's dense rainforests, their responses to human disturbances, such
6 as gun hunting, are not well understood, though the limited studies which have been completed
7 suggest that forest elephants may respond by altering their abundance, distribution, and nocturnal
8 activity. Using Passive Acoustic Monitoring in and around Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park,
9 Republic of Congo, we assess how gun hunting impacts forest elephant occupancy and nighttime
10 vocal activity. Findings reveal that elephant occupancy drops from 0.54 to 0.52 following a
11 gunfire event, a change sustained over eight days. Additionally, increased gunshots led to a
12 significant rise in the proportion of nighttime vocal activity. These behavioral changes can affect
13 forest elephant foraging and reproductive success and their interactions with vegetation,
14 impacting forest growth and function. This study highlights the need for effective conservation
15 strategies to protect the species and their habitats and demonstrates PAM's effectiveness in
16 studying cryptic species in our world's dense, highly biodiverse, and life-sustaining tropical
17 forests.

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22 **Introduction**

23 Tropical forests are the richest ecosystems on Earth (Pimm & Raven 2000; Bradshaw et
24 al. 2009; Gibson et al. 2011), home to about two-thirds of all species (National Research Council
25 1980). However, they face unprecedented threats from deforestation, infrastructure development,
26 resource extraction, agriculture, overconsumption, population growth, and climate change
27 (Laurance & Peres 2006; Bradshaw et al. 2009). These disturbances significantly impact the
28 forests and the species within them, including invertebrates, reptiles, amphibians, mammals, and
29 birds (Newbold et al. 2014). Effective conservation now critically depends on monitoring
30 wildlife in these areas (Nichols & Williams 2006), a challenging task due to the dense vegetation
31 and cryptic nature of many species who reside in these forests.

32 Passive Acoustic Monitoring (PAM) has recently gained recognition as an effective
33 method for monitoring wildlife (Servick 2014) and collecting and interpreting information on
34 species' diversity, abundance, movement, and responses to anthropogenic disturbance (Sueur et
35 al. 2008; Gil et al. 2014; Wrege et al. 2017; Deichmann et al. 2017; Sugai et al. 2019). PAM is
36 an especially useful monitoring tool as it may considerably expand the temporal and spatial
37 scales at which data can be efficiently collected (Van Parjis et al. 2009), especially in
38 traditionally inaccessible and remote locations, such as tropical forests, where rare, elusive, or
39 cryptic species reside (Wrege et al. 2010, 2017).

40 The application of PAM to the study of African forest elephants (*Loxodonta cyclotis*), a
41 cryptic species residing in the Congo Basin, serves as a key example of its benefits for assessing
42 species' communication, activity, behavior, and responses to anthropogenic disturbance (Wrege
43 et al. 2010, 2012, 2017, 2024; Thompson et al. 2010; Swider et al. 2022, 2024; Hedwig et al.
44 2018, 2019). This critically endangered species has experienced a population decline of >80% in

45 the past 93 years (Gobush et al. 2021) due to habitat destruction, climate change, and ivory
46 poaching. Between 2002-2011, they lost 30% of their range and 62% of their population, driven
47 by expanding infrastructure, poor governance, and increased hunting intensity (Maisels et al.
48 2013). Reductions in populations of this keystone species not only have ramifications for the
49 species' existence, but for the structure and function of the Congo Basin, the world's second
50 largest tropical forest which crucially contributes to global carbon sequestration (Molua 2019).
51 As architects and mega-gardeners of the rainforest, forest elephants significantly contribute to
52 maintaining the health and diversity of these ecosystems (Reyna-Hurtado et al. 2023).

53 As architects, forest elephants create natural forest clearings, or "bais," using their tusks
54 and brute strength to access underground mineral water, benefiting various other species (Metsio
55 Sienne et al. 2014; Vanleeuwe et al. 1998; Klaus-Hügi et al. 2000). Their paths through the
56 forest, formed by repeatedly stomping down vegetation, act as firebreaks (Cardoso et al. 2020)
57 and create transnational networks used by Indigenous communities in Central Africa for travel
58 and resource gathering (Remis & Jost 2020). As mega-gardeners, forest elephants disperse seeds
59 through their dung over vast areas; they are capable of moving over 2,800 km annually
60 throughout their average home range of about 700 km² (Mills et al. 2018). Their activity
61 crucially promotes the growth of high wood density species (Berzaghi et al. 2023), so much so
62 that their extinction could decrease carbon stocks by 7%, equivalent to a \$43 billion USD loss in
63 carbon storage services (Berzaghi et al. 2019). This exposes the very critical roles that forest
64 elephants play in maintaining diverse, high-carbon tropical forests (Berzaghi et al. 2019; Reyna-
65 Hurtado et al. 2023).

66 Poaching severely impacts forest elephant numbers and their ecosystem services, but
67 understanding its effects on their behavior and life histories is challenging due to their dense

68 rainforest habitat. Insights from studies on forest elephants' close relative, the African savanna
69 elephant (*Loxodonta africana*), reveal that poaching results in elephants hearing gunshots,
70 encountering poachers, and witnessing deaths, prompting them to remain in undisturbed areas.
71 This results in food competition (Ihwagi et al. 2024), increased rates in aggressive interactions
72 and consequential social and reproductive disruptions (Wittemyer et al. 2007), and genetic
73 isolation, increasing extinction risks (Wilcox & Murphy 1985). Elephants exposed to poaching
74 may become more aggressive towards humans, escalating human-elephant conflict (Compaore et
75 al. 2020). Poaching also skews sex ratios, reduces survivorship, and targets older elephants,
76 disrupting social and ecological knowledge (Wittemyer et al. 2013; Foley et al. 2008). The
77 impacts that poaching may have on elephants are varied, meaning that the species may employ
78 diverse temporal, spatial, and behavioral strategies to minimize human-induced mortality risk.
79 Savanna elephants respond by increasing flight behavior, shifting to nighttime activity, and
80 reducing movement in risky areas (Ihwagi et al. 2024; Gaynor et al. 2018; Graham et al. 2009;
81 Sitati et al. 2003; Wittemyer et al. 2017; Smit et al. 2023; Ihwagi et al. 2018).

82 Research shows that forest elephants respond to human disturbances similarly to savanna
83 elephants. They tend to increase their densities with distance from human activity (Barnes et al.
84 1991; Laurance et al. 2006; Djoko et al. 2022) and actively avoid human settlements and roads,
85 with these features directing their distribution more than ecological factors such as the presence
86 of wetlands and fruit (Buij et al. 2007). In areas with higher human disturbance, forest elephants
87 move less, have smaller home ranges, are less active during the day, and exhibit fewer
88 exploratory movements (Beirne et al. 2021). Previous research has also shown that forest
89 elephants will avoid the site of a poached elephant carcass for eight days (Stephan et al. 2020)
90 and increase their nocturnal activity in response to oil exploration (Wrege et al. 2010).

91 Most studies on forest elephant distribution have used dung sampling methods, revealing
92 that elephants avoid areas with high human activity (Barnes et al. 1991; Yackulic et al. 2011;
93 Buij et al. 2007; Blake 2002; Laurance et al. 2006; Danquah 2016). However, this method is
94 spatially and temporally constrained, often conducted along forest transects, limiting the
95 exploration of forest elephant response at larger spatial scales. Estimating elephant density from
96 dung involves calculating decay rates (Barnes & Jensen 1987), which vary by habitat type,
97 decomposer abundance and diversity, fruit content, and microclimate (White 1995; Mubalama &
98 Sikubwabo 2022; Masunga et al. 2006), making it complex and site-specific (Nchanji &
99 Plumptre 2001; Breuer & Hockemba 2007). Additionally, dung sampling is less effective for
100 monitoring short-term behavioral changes, such as increased nocturnal activity, due to its costs
101 and required human effort.

102 Given that existing population monitoring methods, such as dung sampling, have
103 temporal and spatial constraints, there is growing momentum to apply PAM to studying forest
104 elephant responses to anthropogenic disturbance. Using PAM, researchers can collect acoustic
105 data that not only contains information on elephant vocalizations, but signals representing human
106 activity such as gunshots. When applied across large spatial and temporal scales, PAM can
107 provide valuable insight into the broad patterns of elephant vocalizations and gunshot
108 occurrence. However, this data may also be used to explore elephant response to disturbances
109 such as gunshots at finer scales. For example, a study conducted by Swider et al. 2022 used PAM
110 to examine forest elephant vocal activity throughout the 24-hour period following gun hunting
111 events and found that for the first five hours following the event, vocal activity increased above
112 the control state level, but from hours six to 24, vocal activity dropped below this level. While
113 studies such as this have provided conservation practitioners with valuable insight into forest

114 elephants' vocal response to human activity, knowledge gaps still remain. Primarily, following
115 up on the results of Swider et al. 2022, it is unknown whether observed changes in numbers of
116 detected elephant vocalizations reflect changes in vocal activity or changes in elephants' use of
117 the landscape (e.g., movement in and out of the area). It is also unclear how long it takes for
118 forest elephant vocal activity/landscape use to return to the control state level, or whether this
119 same population's activity is becoming increasingly more nocturnal in response to gun hunting
120 in the area, as has been demonstrated in other populations responding to human activity (Wrege
121 et al. 2010).

122 This study aims to understand the impact of hunting on forest elephants in and around
123 Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park, Republic of Congo, by examining their responses at two
124 different scales. Using PAM, we first assessed changes in forest elephant occupancy over eight
125 days following gun hunting events compared to control events, hypothesizing that gunfire would
126 affect occurrence probability differently across days. A period of eight days was chosen based on
127 the Stephan et al. 2020 study conducted in Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park which found that it
128 took forest elephants eight days to return to the site of a poached elephant carcass. Additionally,
129 we investigated whether the proportion of nighttime calling activity changes in response to gun
130 hunting and examined the influence of habitat, season, protection status, and distance to the
131 nearest mainstem river. Based on previous research conducted on both savanna and forest
132 elephants, we predicted that increased gunfire would correlate with a higher proportion of
133 nighttime calling activity (Graham et al. 2009; Ihwagi et al. 2018). We also expected that open
134 forest habitats, characterized by sparse canopy, greater light penetration into the understory, and
135 increased visibility, would be linked to a greater proportion of nighttime calling activity (Wrege
136 et al. 2024). Additionally, we hypothesized that proximity to rivers would decrease the

137 proportion of nighttime activity due to higher hunting frequency (Swider 2023) while
138 unprotected areas would exhibit a higher proportion of nighttime activity (Gaynor et al. 2018;
139 Graham et al. 2009; Sitati et al. 2003; Wittemyer et al. 2017; Douglas-Hamilton et al. 2005).
140 Lastly, we predicted that the proportion of nighttime calling would increase during the wet
141 season due to the species' reduced hearing range in rainfall.

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144 **Methods**

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146 *Study Area*

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148 The Sangha Trinational Protected Area is composed of four national parks across three
149 Central African countries including the Dzanga-Sangha and Dzanga-Ndoki National Parks in the
150 Central African Republic, Lobéké National Park in Cameroon, and Nouabalé-Ndoki National
151 Park in the Republic of Congo. Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park sits at the core of the Ndoki
152 Forest, which is found between 1.5° to 3°N, and 16° to 17°E and is mainly composed of
153 monodominant *Gilbertiodendron dewevrei* forest, mixed species forest on *terra firma*, and
154 swampy forest (Rollet 1964; Blake & Fay 1997; Breuer et al. 2021). The forest experiences a
155 minimum mean monthly temperature of 21.1 °C and a maximum of 26.6 °C and an average
156 annual rainfall of 1,694 mm (Breuer et al. 2021).

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161 Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park offers a unique opportunity to explore forest elephant
162 activity due to the presence of a landscape-scale acoustic grid managed by the Elephant
163 Listening Project and the Wildlife Conservation Society Congo Program. Acoustic data was
164 collected from a grid of 50 SWIFT acoustic recorders, designed and manufactured by the K. Lisa
165 Yang Center for Conservation Bioacoustics, which were deployed within and around the park in
166 October 2017 (Figure 1). Each acoustic recorder was randomly placed within each of the
167 systematic 25 km² grid cells stratified across the landscape of the study area, which ultimately
168 covers an area of 1,250 km². Each unit was suspended approximately 7-10 meters high on an
169 appropriate tree branch and was left to record continuously for 3-4 months. At the end of this
170 period, the unit was revisited, the SD card and batteries were replaced for the next recording
171 period, and the data were downloaded. The sound data collected from the recorders were stored
172 on 256 GB SD cards as 16-bit WAV files using an 8 kHz sampling rate. The microphones for
173 SWIFT recorders are omnidirectional and can detect rumbles within 0.5 km of the recorder
174 (Wrege et al. 2024) and gunshots within 2.5 km of the recorder (unpublished data from author
175 AKV).

176 To identify elephant and gunshot signals in the sound recordings, we used an elephant
177 rumble detection algorithm (Keen et al. 2017) and gunshot detection algorithm (Wrege et al.
178 2017). For the purposes of this study, only rumble detections that exceeded a likelihood
179 threshold of 0.4 and gunshot detections above 0.53 were tagged and then manually reviewed
180 using Raven Pro (K. Lisa Yang Center for Conservation Bioacoustics & Cornell Lab of
181 Ornithology 2019) to confirm the classification.

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Exploring Broad Temporal Patterns of Forest Elephant Vocal Activity and Hunting Activity

All confirmed rumbles recorded between December 15, 2017, and December 30, 2020, were averaged across hour of day and week of year to illustrate the broad temporal patterns of the population’s vocal activity across this period of time. Rumbles that occurred between hours 0-5 and 18-23 were classified as occurring at “night” and between hours 6-17 as occurring in the “day”, following the patterns of dawn and dusk in the equatorial forests.

All confirmed gunshots recorded between November 24, 2017, and January 25, 2021, were grouped into gunshot events, with gunshots that occurred within one hour of each other at the same recording site being grouped into the same event. The sampling period used to explore the temporal patterns of rumbles was different than the sampling period used to examine hunting activity due to the availability of gunshot and rumble data that had been previously manually reviewed by the Elephant Listening Project (i.e., the gunshot data had two additional months of gunshot detections manually reviewed compared to the rumble data). Once gunshot events were created, we noted that the number of gunshots in a given single event could range from one to 58 gunshots and subsequently divided all events into classes of hunting pressure intensity based on their number of gunshots. “Low” intensity events ranged from 1-5 gunshots, “Medium” intensity events ranged from 6-13 gunshots, and “High” intensity events ranged from 23-58 gunshots. The “intensity” of gunshot events were categorized in this way to attempt to infer more information on the “type” of hunting that was occurring in each gunshot event. For example, based on anecdotal evidence that author AKV obtained from ecoguards in Nouabalé-Ndoki

205 National Park, it is probable that low intensity events represent subsistence hunting activity
206 where non-automatic firearms are discharged at most, five times over the duration of the event
207 by a hunter who is likely hunting smaller wildlife for bushmeat. Alternatively, high intensity
208 events which are characterized by more frequent gunshots within the duration of the event imply
209 that automatic firearms are likely being used to hunt larger, typically more endangered, wildlife
210 such as forest elephants. Events were also classed by whether they occurred during the day or
211 night. Hours 6-17 were also classified as “day” and hours 0-5 and 18-23 were also classified as
212 “night”.

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215 *Occupancy Analysis*

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217 To examine how forest elephant vocal activity and/or landscape use changes across the
218 eight days following a gun hunting event, a dataset of rumbles and gunshots recorded throughout
219 80 days of sound recordings taken between November 28, 2017, and October 3, 2018, was used.
220 From these recordings, 8,421 confirmed rumbles and 112 confirmed gunshots were found from
221 5,018 unique site-date recordings.

222 Gunshots that occurred within one hour of each other and that were recorded at the same
223 recording site were grouped into “events”, resulting in 42 gunshot events. For each gunfire event,
224 we compiled detection histories (i.e., records on whether an elephant was detected or not) for
225 multi-season occupancy models for all sites within 10 km of and including the gunfire event site
226 (following Swider et al. 2022). We also ensured that no other gunfire events occurred within the
227 subsequent eight-day period following the gunfire event across all sites relevant to that event.

228 This sampling approach resulted in the sampling period noted above and in clusters of 5-15 sites
229 (i.e., acoustic recorders) analyzed for each event (mean 9.4 sites per event). Gunfire events only
230 occurred at 27 sites but since data from sites within 10 km of the event site were also included,
231 all 50 sites from the acoustic monitoring grid are represented in the dataset for this analysis.
232 After each gunfire event, we examined the eight days immediately following and designated a
233 primary period (i.e. season; $n = 8$) which was divided into four six-hour secondary sampling
234 periods. Any number of recorded rumbles during a secondary sampling period indicated forest
235 elephant presence.

236 To establish a baseline of elephant activity, for each gunfire event we established a
237 corresponding eight-day control period that was set three to five weeks prior to the gunfire event
238 at the same recording site as the associated gunfire event, resulting in 42 control events. Control
239 periods used the exact same cluster of sites as their corresponding gunfire events, controlling for
240 spatial variation in elephant abundance across the PAM grid sites and ensuring comparability
241 between gunfire and control periods. We ensured that no gunfire events occurred at any sites
242 relevant to the control event within the eight-day control period as well as during the eight-day
243 period preceding the start of the control event. Control period detection histories were compiled
244 in the same manner as those for gunfire events. This method of including multiple control and
245 impact sites (multiple clusters of 5-15 sites), and of staggering control and treatment periods
246 through time rather than simultaneously, is a powerful approach for isolating effects of interest
247 from potentially confounding random events (Underwood 1992, 1994; Walters et al. 1988).

248 We compiled a candidate set of nine multi-season occupancy models that reflected our a
249 priori hypotheses about how forest elephants would respond to gunfire events, either through
250 changes in landscape/site use (represented by the occurrence probability component of the

251 models) or changes in vocal activity (likely reflected in the detection probability component of
252 the models). The fixed effects of interest included ‘GunEvent’ (whether a gunfire event had
253 occurred as opposed to a control period) and its interaction with ‘Day’ (primary periods 1-8). In
254 the global model, both the occurrence and detection probability components were modeled as a
255 function of the interaction between GunEvent and Day. This represents the hypothesis that
256 elephant site use or vocal activity would be different (reduced) following gunfire events than
257 during control periods, but that it would change over the eight subsequent days, perhaps
258 returning to baseline levels (e.g., elephants abandon but then resume use of sites within eight
259 days). We also modeled occurrence and detection as a function of the GunEvent main effect
260 only, representing the hypothesis that post-gunfire site use or vocal activity would differ from
261 control periods, but would not change over the subsequent eight days (e.g., elephants do not
262 resume site use within eight days). The nine candidate models differed in whether the occurrence
263 and detection components incorporated the GunEvent X Day interaction, the GunEvent main
264 effect only, or an intercept only (null model). In the occurrence and detection components of all
265 candidate models, we included Event ID as a random effect to control for the fact that a cluster
266 of multiple sites was analyzed for each gunfire event and control period.

267 We implemented the occupancy models in a Bayesian context using the ‘spOccupancy’
268 package (Doser et al. 2022) in R (R Core Team 2022). We used vague normal priors for both
269 occurrence and detection coefficients. To assess the fit of all candidate models, we performed
270 posterior predictive checks using both the Freeman-Tukey and Chi-squared fit statistics to
271 calculate Bayesian p-values (low values reveal lack of fit; Doser et al. 2022; Kéry & Royle
272 2015). We used the Widely Applicable Information Criteria (WAIC; Watanabe 2010) as a
273 criterion for Bayesian model comparison and calculation of model weights.

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276 *Nighttime Calling Activity Analysis*

277 To examine changes in nighttime calling activity in response to gun hunting, the
278 proportion of nighttime calling activity was compared between 47 days with gunshots and 47
279 control days using recordings collected between December 16, 2017, and December 23, 2020.
280 From these recordings, 301 confirmed rumbles and 137 confirmed gunshots were found from 94
281 unique site-date recordings. Gunfire events were created by grouping together gunshots that were
282 recorded within one hour of each other at the same recording site. The 24-hour period over
283 which elephant rumbles were compiled into “night” and “day” categories began immediately
284 following the end of the gunfire event, and we ensured no other gunshots occurred within this
285 24-hour period. For control events, the 24-hour period over which rumbles were compiled was
286 set to begin exactly three days prior to the gunfire event and at the same recording site, and we
287 ensured no gunshots occurred within this 24-hour period as well.

288 Within the 24-hour periods, rumbles were compiled into “day” and “night” categories
289 based on the pattern of an “elephant day”. An elephant day, as outlined in Wrege et al. 2012, is
290 the 24-hour period beginning at 06:00 on one day and ending at 05:59 the next consecutive day.
291 Formatting the data into elephant days is useful for interpretation of forest elephant activity as
292 previous research at bais has shown that forest elephants are the most active at night between
293 16:30-06:30, meaning that their “days” end closer to 06:00 in the morning rather than at
294 midnight (Fishlock 2010). An elephant day is then divided into a 12-hour day (06:00–17:59) and
295 12-hour night (18:00–05:59) (Wrege et al. 2012; Gessner et al. 2014) to follow the patterns of
296 dawn and dusk in the equatorial forests. Once rumbles were compiled into “night” and “day”

297 categories and to calculate the proportion of nighttime calling activity, we divided the total
298 number of rumbles that occurred in the night by the total number of rumbles that occurred during
299 the 24-hour period that immediately followed the end of the gunfire or control event.

300 The total number of gunshots recorded for each 24-hour period was also calculated and
301 used as a predictor in the model. Additional covariates include protection status (whether the
302 recording site was located in a protected area or a logging concession), season (defined below),
303 proportion of open forest (defined below) located within 600 meters of the recording site,
304 distance between the recording site and the nearest mainstem river, and an interaction between
305 protection status and the number of gunshots. Recording site and event pair were also included as
306 random effects in the model in order to control for any unknown variability associated with
307 specific recording sites or event pairs (e.g., hunting and/or elephant presence might be higher at
308 some sites versus others).

309 To determine season, long-term seasonal trends based on rainfall data collected by the
310 Goualougo Triangle Ape Project in the Goualougo Triangle of Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park,
311 which falls approximately in the center of the acoustic grid, were used. The trends revealed that
312 the dry season (< 60 mm of rainfall per month) occurs between December-February. The
313 distance between each recording site and the nearest mainstem of the Ndoki or Goualougo river
314 (whichever was closest) was measured using GIS watercourse layers. Layers were created by
315 manually tracing digital elevation models and were then confirmed with on-the-ground GPS
316 mapping conducted during routine acoustic grid maintenance. A random forest classifier was
317 created for habitat classification and had an overall accuracy of 0.91 and a Kappa coefficient of
318 0.86 (Swider et al. in prep). For the open forest class, the model had a producer's accuracy and
319 user's accuracy of 0.94. Using the classifier, the proportion of open forest within 600 meters of

320 each recording site was then quantified. Open forest includes habitats associated with water such
321 as river floodplains with sparse or open canopy, open canopy swamps, open water (rivers),
322 aquatic vegetation and grasses, and bais and other small clearings known as “eyangas”.

323 Regression models were used and fitted to a binomial family as the response variable is a
324 proportion. Models were developed using the glmmTMB R package (Brooks et al. 2017). The
325 most parsimonious model among candidate models was chosen based on AICc (Burnham &
326 Anderson 2004) and using the AICcmodavg (Mazerolle 2023) package in RStudio Version
327 2023.03.0. We also checked the assumptions of the top models to avoid overfitting and to ensure
328 the validity of the conclusions drawn from the model selection process. Model diagnostics for
329 our three top models indicated good performance (Appendix S1 Figures 1, 2, & 3). Plots were
330 created in R (version 1.47.5, R Core Team (2023)) using built-in base functions, as well as
331 functions from ggplot2 (version 3.3.2, Wickham 2016).

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334 **Results**

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336 *Exploring Broad Temporal Patterns of Forest Elephant Vocal Activity and Hunting Activity*

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338 We found that forest elephant call rates were generally higher during the beginning of the
339 year, peaking mid-year, with similar rates of activity during the day and night (Figure 2). In
340 contrast, higher intensity gun hunting activity was most common during the daytime (Figures 3a,
341 3b, & 3c).

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Occupancy Analysis

For control events, the average daily forest elephant call rate was 0.50 with a minimum daily call rate of 0.27 and a maximum of 0.63. For gunfire events, the average daily call rate was 0.47 with a minimum daily call rate of 0.39 and a maximum of 0.56 (see Figure 4 for an illustration).

Four of our candidate models were moderately supported (model weights > 0.10), and others had some support (Table 1). Given that no particular model unambiguously outperformed all others (model weights ranged from 0.014 to 0.273; Table 1), we chose to model average predictions from all candidate models to estimate occurrence probability of forest elephants in the presence and absence of gunfire events.

Occurrence probabilities were lower following gunfire events (0.52) than during control periods (0.54), and remained relatively stable over the eight-day period (Figure 5a), demonstrating that there is a slight reduction in the population’s use of sites within 10 km of the gunfire event. For occurrence probability, the average value for any of the eight days following a gunfire event never increases to the level of any of the average values of the eight days following a control event (Figure 5a; Appendix S1 Table 1), revealing that forest elephant occurrence probability does not return to “baseline” within the eight-day period examined. During the first few days following gunfire events, detection probabilities were slightly lower than during the initial days of control periods; gunfire event and control period detection probabilities converged around day five (Figure 5b; Appendix S1 Table 2).

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367 *Nighttime Calling Activity Analysis*

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369 Three models were well-supported ($\Delta AICc < 2$; Burnham and Anderson 2002), with all
370 models including effects of the number of gunshots and season (Table 2). Our top model also
371 included a positive effect of the proportion of open forest within 600 meters of the recording site.
372 Our second best-supported model was the same as the first, excluding the effect of proportion of
373 open forest. Our third best-supported model included the same effects as our top model but
374 additionally contained the effect of protection status of the forest and the interaction effect
375 between protection status and the number of gunshots. The most parsimonious model was used
376 to interpret results from the data.

377 In line with our predictions, the proportion of nighttime calling activity was positively
378 associated with the number of gunshots ($\beta = 1.3741$, $SE = 0.4956$, $z = 2.7727$; Figure 6a) and the
379 proportion of open forest ($\beta = 5.3412$, $SE = 2.5846$, $z = 2.0665$; Figure 6b). However, contrary
380 to our prediction on season, the wet season was negatively associated with the proportion of
381 nighttime calling activity ($\beta = -3.9529$, $SE = 1.4632$, $z = -2.7015$; Figure 6c). To confirm the
382 reliability of using the first top model to interpret results, we examined the effect of protection
383 found only in the third top model and noted a slightly higher proportion of nighttime calling
384 activity in logging concessions compared to the national park, though the difference was small
385 (0.004), and the confidence intervals overlapped significantly (Appendix S1 Table 3; Appendix
386 S1 Figure 4). Estimates of coefficients and standard errors for all predictors included in the top
387 three models can be seen in Figure 7.

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389

390 **Discussion**

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392 Our results show how forest elephants are being impacted by gun hunting, revealing that
393 both occurrence and detection probabilities were slightly lower following gunfire events
394 compared to control periods. Additionally, the proportion of nighttime calling activity was
395 positively associated with the number of gunshots and the proportion of open forest, while the
396 wet season had a negative impact.

397 Our findings directly expand on a previous study demonstrating changes in forest
398 elephant call rates in the 24 hours following gunfire events (Swider et al. 2022). Swider et al.
399 (2022) acknowledged that the observed decline in elephant call detections may reflect elephants'
400 shift in landscape use away from the disturbance or a reduction in vocal activity. In the present
401 study, we employ an occupancy approach in an effort to differentiate between changes in
402 landscape use versus changes in vocal activity. Occupancy models contain separate model
403 components for occurrence and detection probabilities, so that estimates of species occurrence
404 are not confounded by potential changes in the probability of detecting the species (MacKenzie
405 et al. 2002). The occupancy approach allows us to potentially disentangle changes in elephant
406 landscape use from changes in vocal activity because shifts in landscape use should primarily
407 influence the occurrence model component while changes in vocal activity are likely to manifest
408 in the detection model component (call rates will impact the probability of acoustically detecting
409 a vocal species). By analyzing additional gunfire events and expanding the analysis period of
410 Swider et al. 2022 to cover an eight-day period following gunfire events, we sought to determine
411 the duration of any shifts in landscape use and/or vocal activity. While we found no clear pattern

412 in model averaged detection probabilities (Figure 5b), we revealed a slight difference in
413 occurrence probabilities between gunfire and control events (Figure 5a). Although this difference
414 was minor, our findings demonstrate a prolonged shift in forest elephant landscape use away
415 from gunfire event sites for more than eight days (i.e., occurrence probabilities did not return to
416 control levels during the eight days under investigation). This suggests that the eight-day period
417 with which we chose to explore forest elephant response was not long enough to capture the
418 return of their behavior to the control state.

419 Changes in forest elephant occupancy may impact the species' interactions with
420 vegetation, affecting trophic dynamics (Patten et al. 2019) and forest growth and function,
421 ultimately eroding carbon storage services (Bello et al. 2015). Similar to savanna elephants,
422 forest elephants might compress into safer areas, leading to superabundance and vegetation
423 damage (Barnes 1983; Lewis 1986). Forest elephants are attracted to mast fruiting events (White
424 1994; Blake & Fay 1997; Morgan & Lee 2007), but a decrease in their use of these areas may
425 reduce their foraging and ranging behaviors, affecting body conditions and associated biological
426 processes. Changes in forest elephant occupancy in certain areas of the forest may also increase
427 human-elephant conflict in areas where the population feels more secure, negatively affecting the
428 species' conservation (Breuer et al. 2016).

429 Results of the proportion of nighttime calling activity analysis indicate that, as we
430 predicted, forest elephants increase the proportion of their nighttime calling activity as gun
431 hunting intensifies, consistent with previous studies that have examined fear-based responses of
432 both savanna (Smit et al. 2023; Gaynor et al. 2018; Graham et al. 2009; Sitati et al. 2003;
433 Wittemyer et al. 2017) and forest elephants (Wrege et al. 2012). In line with our prediction on
434 habitat, we also found that as the proportion of open forest increases, so does the proportion of

435 nighttime calling activity, supporting the findings of previous research which has demonstrated
436 that forest elephant activity is strongly nocturnal in open forest areas (Wrege et al. 2024). This
437 behavior is likely due to the population's increased visibility to hunters in this habitat, which
438 allows more light through the canopy and consists of a more open forest structure. Counter to our
439 prediction, we found that the dry season was associated with a higher proportion of nighttime
440 calling activity, possibly because elephants spend more time near water sources in the dry season
441 (Swider 2023; Blake 2002), making them more vigilant in these areas with higher hunting
442 activity. While we did not find an effect of distance to the nearest mainstem river on the
443 proportion of nighttime calling activity, which is further supported by previous research (Breuer
444 et al. 2021), it is possible that this effect is being masked by the effect of the dry season. Future
445 research may explore if there is an interaction effect between season and distance to nearest
446 mainstem river in order to investigate whether this may be the case. We also did not find an
447 effect of protection status of the forest on the proportion of nighttime calling activity as we had
448 originally predicted. We note that up until 2020, gunshots were recorded both in and out of the
449 national park, indicating that it is possible that the effect of increased protection was not captured
450 by this dataset. However, the combined efforts of conservation practitioners working in
451 Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park have resulted in no gunshots being detected across the acoustic
452 grid since 2021. While this means that we may not have the data to further explore the effects of
453 protection status on nocturnal activity, this is a compelling example of successful conservation
454 for this critical species and the biodiversity that depends on them. Moreover, our results from our
455 investigation into the broad temporal patterns of forest elephant vocal activity and hunting
456 activity provide compelling examples of how PAM may be utilized to provide conservationists

457 with information on the broad patterns of wildlife and human activity in the areas they are
458 working to protect.

459 Although gun hunting has decreased in and around Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park, it
460 persists elsewhere in forest elephants' range, potentially affecting nighttime calling activity
461 widely. Vocalizations are crucial for maintaining group cohesion in dense forests (Thompson
462 2009), and shifts in vocal activity to the nighttime may disrupt social behaviors like meeting
463 family members or finding mates, impacting population size (Wittemyer et al. 2007). The risk of
464 being near hunters (i.e., death) drives elephants to adopt avoidance strategies, including temporal
465 niche partitioning. However, these shifts in vocal activity may alter the important intraspecific
466 interactions that occur between individuals. For example, in savanna elephants, rumbles allow
467 individuals to communicate information about their identity (McComb et al. 2000), their
468 emotional state (Soltis et al. 2005; Soltis et al. 2009), and external threats that they may be aware
469 of (Soltis et al. 2014). In forest elephants, changes in vocal activity in social settings such as bais,
470 where elephants share information and establish social and ecological traditions (Fishlock et al.
471 2016), may consequentially impact their biology, sociality, and cognition.

472 The results of this study have provided insight into how forest elephants are responding
473 to gun hunting, having implications for their monitoring and conservation (Breuer et al. 2016).
474 The demonstrated shifts in their behavior provide evidence that nontarget elephants in the
475 vicinity of gunfire events are also affected, shifting their vocal activity to the night and sustaining
476 changes in their local habitat use for at least eight days following gun hunting. Reductions in safe
477 spatial and temporal niches may have ramifications for the species' population size, genetic
478 fitness, group cohesion, and the social learning and relationships that are vital for their survival.
479 These reductions may also influence forest structure and reduce our planet's ability to sequester

480 carbon (Berzaghi et al. 2019) if the Congo Basin’s mega-gardeners and architects choose to
481 depart vital parts of the forest and compress into more secure areas.

482

483

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497

498

499 **Conflict of Interest**

500 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

501

502

503 **Data Availability Statement**

504 Data and code will be made available to the journal upon acceptance of the paper. However, if it
505 is required sooner, please let us know.

506

507

508 **Artificial Intelligence (AI) Declaration**

509 The web-based AI tool, ChatGTP, was used to reduce the word count of this manuscript but was
510 not utilized or applied in any other way in the development, analysis, presentation, or
511 interpretation of these studies.

512

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Figures

Figure 1 A map of the study site depicting the grid of 50 acoustic recorders, located in portions of NNNP and adjacent logging concessions. Rivers are shown in blue and ephemeral logging roads are shown in grey. The red dot in the insert map corresponds with the approximate location of the study site in the northern Republic of Congo.

Figure 2 Average forest elephant call rate by week of year (x-axis) and hour of day (y-axis), compiled from acoustic data collected in and around Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park, Republic of Congo between December 2017-2020. Brighter colors correspond with higher call rates. Horizontal white dashed lines mark the transition between “night” and “day”, with night occurring between hours 0-5 and 18-23 and day occurring between hours 6-17, following the patterns of dawn and dusk in the equatorial forests. As seen from the figure, forest elephant call rates are generally higher in the beginning of the year than the end, with the highest vocal activity occurring towards the middle of the year. We also note that across each week, calling activity typically occurred at similar rates throughout the night and day.

Figure 3a Count of low hunting pressure gun events (1-5 gunshots within the event) recorded across an acoustic grid located in and around Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park, Republic of Congo between 2017-2021. We note that low hunting pressure events occur throughout both day and night.

*An “event” consists of gunshots that were recorded within one hour of each other on the same recording unit.

*Hours 0–5 and 18–23 correspond with “night” and hours 6–17 correspond with “day”, following the patterns of dawn and dusk in the equatorial forests.

Figure 3b Count of medium hunting pressure gun events (6-13 gunshots within the event) recorded across an acoustic grid located in and around Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park, Republic of Congo between 2017-2021. We note that medium hunting pressure events occur most often during the day.

*An “event” consists of gunshots that were recorded within one hour of each other on the same recording unit.

*Hours 0–5 and 18–23 correspond with “night” and hours 6–17 correspond with “day”, following the patterns of dawn and dusk in the equatorial forests.

Figure 3c Count of high hunting pressure gun events (23-58 gunshots within the event) recorded across an acoustic grid located in and around Nouabalé-Ndoki National Park, Republic of Congo between 2017-2021. We note that high hunting pressure events occur only during the day.

*An “event” consists of gunshots that were recorded within one hour of each other on the same recording unit.

*Hours 0–5 and 18–23 correspond with “night” and hours 6–17 correspond with “day”, following the patterns of dawn and dusk in the equatorial forests.

Figure 4 Average forest elephant call rate throughout the eight days following a gunshot and control event. The dashed vertical lines divide the x-axis into individual “days”.

Figure 5 (a) Occurrence probability and associated SE plotted over the eight day period for both gunfire and control events and (b) detection probability and associated SE plotted over the eight day period for both gunfire and control events.

Figure 6 Positive association between the proportion of night calls and (a) number of gunshots, (b) proportion of open forest within 600 meters of the recording site, and (c) dry season, as predicted by the best supported model.

Figure 7 Estimates of coefficients and standard error for each variable included in the top three models.

Tables

Table 1 Output of nine candidate models for the occupancy analysis.

Rank	Occupancy fixed covariates	Detection fixed covariates	Occ. and det. random effect	WAIC	Δ WAIC	Weight
1	GunEvent	.	Event ID	9874.914	0	0.273
2 (Null)	.	.	Event ID	9875.515	0.601	0.202
3	.	GunEvent*Day	Event ID	9875.799	0.885	0.175
4	.	GunEvent	Event ID	9876.377	1.464	0.131
5	GunEvent	GunEvent*Day	Event ID	9877.062	2.148	0.093
6	GunEvent	GunEvent	Event ID	9877.692	2.778	0.068
7	GunEvent*Day	.	Event ID	9879.328	4.414	0.030
8	GunEvent*Day	GunEvent	Event ID	9880.806	5.892	0.014
9 (Global)	GunEvent*Day	GunEvent*Day	Event ID	9880.911	5.997	0.014

Table 2 Output from the top four candidate models for the nighttime calling activity analysis, with the top three models falling within $\Delta AICc < 2$.

*Note that all models had [+ (1|Site)] and [+ (1|Pair)] included as random effects for “Site” and “Pair” respectively.

Model Rank	Model Description	AICc	$\Delta AICc$	AICc Weight	Log-Likelihood	df
1	NumShots + PropOpen600m + Season	121.75	0.00	0.23	-54.39	6
2	NumShots + Season	122.77	1.02	0.14	-56.04	5
3	NumShots + PropOpen600m + Season + Protection + NumShots*Protection	122.95	1.20	0.13	-52.63	8
4	NumShots + PropOpen600m + Season + Protection	123.78	2.03	0.08	-54.24	7

Appendix

Figures

Appendix S1 Figure 1 Results from tests completed on the best supported model using the plot function in the DHARMA package.

DHARMA residual

Appendix S1 Figure 2 Results from tests completed on the second best supported model using the plot function in the DHARMA package.

DHARMA residual

Appendix S1 Figure 3 Results from tests completed on the third best supported model using the plot function in the DHARMA package.

Appendix S1 Figure 4 Proportion of night calls (y-axis) for both national park and logging concession, as predicted by the third top-model.

Tables

Appendix S1 Table 1 Estimates of coefficients and standard errors for occurrence probability. G0 corresponds with control events and G1 corresponds with gunfire events.

Day	G0 (control)	G1 (gunfire)	G0 SE	G1 SE
1	0.5394406	0.5229949	0.05447942	0.0362488
2	0.5390778	0.5229372	0.05418435	0.03596842
3	0.5387088	0.5228785	0.05398187	0.03575545
4	0.5383345	0.5228192	0.05390069	0.03563404
5	0.5379557	0.5227595	0.05395375	0.0356245
6	0.5375734	0.5226995	0.05413101	0.03573
7	0.5371887	0.5226395	0.05440778	0.03593338
8	0.5368025	0.5225797	0.05475668	0.03620945

Days 1-8 Avg:	0.53813525	0.5227885	0.054224444	0.035888005
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Appendix S1 Table 2 Estimates of coefficients and standard errors for detection probability. G0 corresponds with control events and G1 corresponds with gunfire events.

Day	G0 (control)	G1 (gunfire)	G0 SE	G1 SE
1	0.1952442	0.186471	0.02900392	0.01635445
2	0.1905601	0.18447	0.0271053	0.01569864
3	0.1861687	0.1825353	0.02566311	0.01521848
4	0.1820739	0.1806664	0.0247014	0.01493067
5	0.1782734	0.1788629	0.02419564	0.01483577
6	0.1747601	0.1771239	0.0240704	0.01491362
7	0.171523	0.1754485	0.02422165	0.01512911
8	0.1685483	0.1738356	0.02454734	0.01544308

Days 1-8 Avg:	0.180893963	0.1799267	0.025438595	0.015315478
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Appendix S1 Table 3 Estimates of predicted means, standard errors, and confidence intervals for the proportion of nighttime calling activity for both logging concession areas and national park, as predicted by the third top-model.

Location	Mean	Standard Error	Low CI	High CI
Logging Concession	0.9964914	1.838386	0.8855271	0.9999041
National Park	0.9923224	1.437633	0.8853437	0.9995380